

A proposal for the entomological collection workflow to study diversity applied to forensics and conservation: from the field to data publishing.

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A good corporative workflow allows defining and following tasks to execute a particular process properly. The excessive number of functions involved in the biological collections operation might become overwhelming without a suitable, precise, and efficient workflow. The entomological collection in the Tecnológico de Antioquia, Institución Universitaria (CETdeA), focused on forensic importance flies, took the challenge together with its staff of proposing a logical strategical plan. This proposal encompasses academic Integrity, willingness to serve, teamwork, and quality processes to bring on the workflow proposal. Four macro-processes are recognized as follows: administrative management, biological sample processing, physical space management, and visualization of the collection.

In detail, such processes include field working conform the environmental legislation, curatorial process, specimens loans and donations, processes involved in morphological and genetic analysis (morphometrics, DNA extraction, amplification, and sequencing), info publication on the global infrastructure data networks (GBIF, CBOL, GenBank), up to publishing processes about alpha taxonomy, bionomy, systematics, species distribution modeling in high impact journals. The Methodology of the collection alludes to perceiving biological specimens not only as a physical element but a more integrative vision. Within the concept of the extended specimen, an approach where biological entities deposited in collections contribute to the knowledge of biodiversity, promote research teaching, and build a framework from the basic research to the applied forensic entomology and conservation biology as here is detailed exposed.

